

THE INFLUENCES OF PARTICLE SIZES ON PERFORMANCE OF BIODEGRADABLE WOOD PLASTIC COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED FROM LINGO-CELLULOSIC AGRICULTURAL WASTE

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ABSTRACT

Limited supply of wood products and at the same time high demand driven by ongoing population growth is motivating research into new sources of raw material in an attempt to reduce pressure on forest resources. Cotton stalk waste is a potential alternative lingo-cellulose material that can be used as feedstock material for the manufacture of wood plastic composites (WPCs). Unlike many other agri-waste sources, cotton stalk are comparable to common hardwood species in respect to their fibrous structure and composition. The objective of this research was to evaluate the effects of opening particle sizes (a size sieve used for the manufacture of particles) and particle load on the performance of wood plastic composites made from entire cotton stalks with Biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA). Three opening particle sizes (1 mm, 0.5 mm and 0.25 mm) and particle weight fraction (20% and 50%) were investigated in this research. It was found that there was not much differences in terms of tensile strength and water absorption between composites containing particle sizes of 1 mm and 0.5 mm. The highest tensile strength and lowest water uptake were observed in composites with particle size of 0.25 mm. The particle weight fraction had a significantly adverse effect on tensile strength and moisture uptake. The tensile modulus of composites containing particle sizes of 1mm and 0.5 mm was decreased with increasing particle weigh fraction. Conversely, this property was increased with particles of 0.25 mm.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global demand for wood, wood based panels and wood plastic composites has rapidly increased in recent decades and it is predicted to continue to grow due to ongoing population growth globally. The international average annual growth rate of sawn timber consumption for the period of 2020 to 2030 was estimated around 1.4% and the figure for wood based panels at the same period was also projected about 2.9% [1]. Global wood plastic composite production was approximately 4.2 million tons in 2016 and that figure is anticipated to almost double by 2022 to 8.76 billion USD [2]. This results in high pressure on diminishing forest resources. Consequently, research into alternative fiber resources for cellulosic based products in general and wood plastic composites in particular, has been highly encouraged. Agricultural residues are potential alternative lino-cellulose feedstocks to forestry based sourced woody feedstocks. Cotton stalks are widely regarded as one of the more promising alternatives available in Australia. This is not only due to the abundance of the resource but

also to the fact that the residues present a negative value to the cotton farmer. In addition, cotton stalks are comparable to most hard wood species in terms of fibrous structure and composition [3].

In Australia cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum L.*) is cultivated only in Queensland and New South Wales with the five-year average area to 2015-2016 being 372,000 hectares [4]. One hectare of cotton generates roughly three tons of dry stalks [5, 6]. This indicates that there are approximately 1,160,000 tons of cotton stalks produced in Australia annually. Furthermore, almost all of this waste is burnt at the field leading to air pollution [7, 8], soil erosion and decrease in soil biological activity [9]. If incorporated into the soil it promotes the spread of pests during the winter [10]. Consequently, burning of cotton stalk waste or incorporating this waste into the soil not only results in serious environmental issues and soil problems but also wastes a potentially underutilized resource.

A number of cotton stalk based filled/reinforced thermoplastic composites have been investigated in literature. In these investigations the authors fabricated composites by combining cotton stalk fibres or cotton stalk bark with polypropylene (PP) or high density polyethylene (HDPE). Qi, C., K. Guo, and Y. Liu [11] conducted a study on the effect of fiber sizes and fiber thermal treatment temperatures on the performance of cotton stalk fibers and HDPE composites using hot press molding. Three different fiber length (fine: 20 mesh, short: fiber length 5 – 15 mm, and long: fiber length; 450 mm) and four thermal treatment temperatures (100, 120, 140, and 170°C). This study reported that the mechanical properties increased with increasing size of cotton stalk bundles and the lowest thickness swelling was seen in composite with particle treated at 170°C. Seedahmed, A.I [10] evaluate the mechanical properties of cotton stalks reinforce polypropylene composites with ratios of 95/5, 90/10, 85/15, 80/20 and 75/25 (polypropylene (PP)/ cotton stalk fibers (CSF)). The specimens of oriented fiber composites were prepared by a combination of injection-molding and compression-molding techniques. The test results of this research are presented in Table 1.

Composition %		Mechanical properties	
Polypropylene	Cotton stalks	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elastic Modulus(GPa)
100	0	22.23	1.31
95	5	28.40	1.43
90	10	33.32	1.62
85	15	33.92	1.78
80	20	35.40	1.99
75	25	38.00	2.17

Table 1 Mechanical properties of PP-CS composites at different compositions

In order to investigate the influence of cotton stalk bark (CSB) on properties of composites Wu, H., et al.,[12] processed dried cotton stalk bark from cotton stem by milling into 200 mesh powder. The powder was then mixed with Polypropylene in four different mass ratios (2.5wt%, 5wt%, 10wt%, 15wt%, and 30wt%). 2.5wt% pp-g-MA and 2.5wt% Stearic acid was added during the compounding process. The effects of CSB on the PP-CSB composites are shown in Table 2.

Types of composites	Flexural modulus (MPa)	Flexural strengths (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (MPa)	Tensile strengths (MPa)
PP	1120 ± 21	37.3± 0.3	171± 5	36.5 ± 0.1
PP-CSB-2.5	1273 ± 30	40.1± 0.4	175± 10	34.8± 0.3
PP-CSB-5	1393 ± 9	41.3± 0.3	178± 14	34.1± 0.6
PP-CSB-10	1555 ± 15	43.7± 0.3	182± 7	33.9± 0.5
PP-CSB-15	1762 ± 16	45.5± 0.8	195 ± 8	33.7 ± 0.5
PP-CSB-30	2128 ± 21	48.4± 0.8	216± 9	32.9 ± 0.3

Table 2 Mechanical properties of PP-CSB composites at different CSB fraction

There is no information about the effects of opening particle sizes of cotton stalk and particle load on the performance of Cotton stalk PHA composites. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effects

of opening particle sizes (1 mm, 0.5 mm and 0.25 mm) and particle weight fraction (20% and 50%) on performance of wood plastic composites manufactured from entire cotton stalks and Biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA).

2 MATERIAL AND METHOD

The cotton stalks used in this study were harvested at Goodar, Queensland. After harvesting this resource was air-dried to a moisture content of around 20 %. Following this, whole cotton stalks were converted in to chips by using a domestic chipping machine and the chips were milled into three different particle categories by a laboratory cutting mill (Retsch). Three different size sieves (1mm, 0.5mm and 0.25mm) were used to produce three cut-off grades. All grades were subsequently conditioned to a moisture content of 12% prior to particle size analysis.

Particle analysis was carried out with a laboratory sieve shaker. Each milled grade was sorted into six sub-group categories using five different metal sieves with opening sizes of: 0.5 mm, 0.3 mm, 0.212 mm, 0.150 mm, 0.090 mm. 100 gram of material was analyzed. The shaking duration was 10 minutes and five replications were performed for each grade. The distribution of particle size was calculated as a percentage according, $P_i = (W_i/W) * 100\%$. Where P_i : Percentage of particles on the sieve i compared to total mass of particles (%); W_i : Mass of particles on the sieve i (gram); W : Total mass of particles (gram)

All three types of particles were dried by using a vacuum oven at temperature of 80°C and 80 KPa pressure to moisture content of 0% (after 12 hours, particles were weighed every an hour until the results of three successive were constant). Subsequently, particles were mixed with PHBV (Y1010, from Enmat, Tianan China) according to ratios as shown in Table 3 by using a kitchen blender. The mixture was then re-dried at 60°C for a duration of 4 hours to ensure moisture content of 0% before extrusion.

Types of composites	Opening fiber size (mm)	Fiber wt%	Polymer wt%
A	1	20	80
B	1	50	50
C	0.5	20	80
D	0.5	50	50
E	0.25	20	80
F	0.25	50	50

Table 3: Composite types

A co-rotating twin screw extruder with a diameter of 16 mm and a length-to-diameter ratio of 40:1 was used for the manufacture of samples. The blended material was feed in the first zone, material was flood fed and screw speed was set to 100 rpm. The barrel temperature profile shown in Table 4 was used. A slit die with cross section dimension of 13 x 2mm was employed to yield sections of rectangular samples for mechanical tests

Zone	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Zone 5	Zone 6	Zone 7	Zone 8	Zone 9	Zone 10	Die
Temperature (°C)	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	165	160	160

Table 4 : Temperature profile

The samples were conditioned prior to testing at 25°C and 50% relative humidity for two weeks. This is important as PHBV undergoes slow crystallization during the conditioning phase.

Tensile strength and tensile module were conducted according to ASTM D638. Specimens were cut according to Type V “dogbone” by using a laser cutter. The number of test specimens was 10 for each composite type. Water absorption after 2 hours, 24 hours, and 168 hours immersion in water with 5 test specimens were conducted for each kind of composite type in accordance with ASTM D570.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Particles’ screening average distribution by weight and standard deviation of three different opening particle size categories (1 mm, 0.5 mm, and 0.25 mm) are shown in Figure 1. In general, there were different distribution of particle sizes between three opening particle sizes (1mm, 0.5 mm and 0.25 mm). Looking at more details, the distribution of particle in sub-group (between 0.3 and 0.212 mm sieves, between 0.212 and 0.150 mm sieves, between 0.150 and 0.090 mm sieves, and pass through 0.090 mm sieve) of opening particle size grades of 1 mm and 0.5 mm were almost the same. In contrast, the distribution of particle sizes of opening particle size of 0.25 mm were significant compared to opening particle sizes of 1 mm and 0.5 mm in all sub-groups with exception of sub-group particles passed through 0.090 mm sieve.

Figure 1: Average weigh distribution of three opening particle grades

Figure 2: Effect of particle size and particle load on tensile strength

Figure 3: : Effect of particle size and particle load on tensile modulus

The tensile strength and tensile modulus are shown in Figure 2 and 3. Overall, both the mean tensile strength and the tensile modulus of all cotton-stalk PHBV composites are lower than those of pure PHBV. The mean tensile strength of all cotton-stalk PHBV composite types was significantly decreased and the strength reduction increased with filler loading. Similarly, the mean tensile modulus of composites containing opening particle sizes of 1 mm and 0.5 mm was decreased with increasing cotton stalk load (20wt% to 50wt%). However, the opposite trend was seen in composite containing opening particle size of 0.25 mm, where the modulus increased with the increase in filler content. This means that with the exception of tensile modulus of composite containing opening particle size of 0.25 mm, the increase in cotton stalk load leads to having negative impacts on tensile strength and tensile modulus of the composite.

It also can be seen in Figure 2 that there is not much difference in terms of mean tensile strength between composites containing opening particle sizes of 1 mm and 0.5 mm, respectively. The highest average tensile strength was observed in composite with 0.25 mm opening particle size. This can be explained as small particles leading to better even between fiber and polymer.

Figure 4: Effect of particle size and particle load on water absorption after 2, 24 and 168 hours

The average water uptake after immersion in water for 2 hours, 24 hours, and 168 hours of all composite types is shown in Figure 3 and reveals that the water absorption of all composites noticeably increased with increasing cotton stalk loading from 20wt% to 50wt%. This is because lingo-cellulose fibers are hygroscopic materials; consequently, the higher ratio of lingo-cellulose leads to higher percentage of water uptake. The average proportion of water absorption of composites with opening particle sizes of 1 mm and 0.5 mm was almost for all immersion durations. The lowest average water absorption was recorded in composites containing opening particle size of 0.25 mm.

The findings from this investigation can be compared with other wood plastic composites to determine the benefit of agricultural waste cotton stalks as a source of raw material for composite manufacture. As shown in Figure 2 and 3, one can see that the obtained properties in this research compare well against commercially available products. It is worth noting that the Wood Plastic Composite (WPC) produced in this research consists entirely of bio-degradable and bio-based constituents. This is in contrast to the commercial WPCs which predominately use Polyolefins.

4 Conclusion

The tensile strength as well as water absorption of composites with opening particle sizes of 1 mm and 0.5 mm were almost the same. The highest tensile strength and lowest water absorption were recorded in composites containing opening particle size of 0.25 mm. This is an interesting finding as typically, at least for the mechanical properties, one would expect better performance for higher aspect ratios. Based on the method used to characterize we can not make any assessment of the aspect ratio of the particles. In fact, it is entirely possible, that the smaller particles have higher aspect ratios. The fact that water absorption is lower for small particle sizes also suggests that smaller particles are better encapsulated in the polymer matrix. Better mixing, dispersion and encapsulation could indeed explain all the phenomena observed.

It is encouraging that the properties obtained in this research are comparable with values typically seen in commercial WPCs. The chosen PHBV matrix makes the composite completely bio-degradable which is not the case for most other WPC formulations currently available. Filling the PHBV with a low cost, or in the case of PHBV negative value agrifibre waste product, also helps to combat the costs of the resulting total cost of the composite. This is particularly important for this combination as PHBV is currently significantly more expensive than any of the commodity thermoplastics regularly used in WPCs.

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